

A Light-Curable Plant-Protein-Based Colloid Produced Through Controlled High-pH Treatment

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Abstract

This work summarizes observations relating to a plant-protein-based imaging system with a specific focus on alternative photographic printing applications. Protein dispersions are produced through controlled highly alkaline modification. Under these conditions, proteins are expected to undergo structural and chemical changes including deamidation, partial hydrolysis, altered aggregation behavior, and modification of intermolecular interactions.

These colloidal dispersions exhibit high water solubility, improved wetting, reduced viscosity, and are photo-crosslinkable with multiple classes of light-sensitive compounds including those used in alternative photographic printing. Bench-scale observations including ammonia release, surface tension, altered precipitation behavior, haze, pigment dispersion, and practical printing results were recorded.

Emphasis is placed on iron-based sensitizer systems due to their accessibility, comparatively low toxicity, and established role within alternative photographic practice. The work further explores how modified plant-protein dispersions may contribute to more materially sustainable printmaking processes through renewable plant-derived materials, compatibility with comparatively lower-toxicity sensitizer systems, and reduced hazardous waste generation.

Fig. 1. Completed four-colour print (CMYK) (30 cm x 46 cm) produced using a high-pH treated wheat-protein-based colloid.

Fig. 2. Detail crop of Figure 1 demonstrating low grain and tonal continuity.

1. Background

Alternative photographic printing processes such as gum-bichromate (direct carbon), carbon printing, and related colloidal systems rely on differential photochemical crosslinking or insolubilization within a pigmented emulsion layer, utilizing pigments dispersed within gelatin, gum, or other colloidal binders in combination with organic or inorganic sensitizers. Traditional dichromate-based systems employ toxic hexavalent chromium compounds, while ferric (iron)-based processes are generally regarded as having substantially lower toxicity and environmental impact.

Related ferric-salt based imaging systems have historical precedents in mid-20th-century graphic arts and screen-printing applications. More recently, ferric-salt approaches have also been referred to in some contexts as the “Chiba system,” particularly in connection with direct carbon and carbon printing workflows documented in the early 2000s.

Plant-protein dispersions are a potential alternative class of colloidal binders for such imaging systems. Controlled high-pH treatment substantially alters their viscosity, solubility, wetting behavior, and film-forming characteristics, enabling their use in light-curable imaging and stencil-forming applications.

2. Protein Modification and Dispersion Behavior

Plant protein isolates of wheat, soy, and yellow pea were subjected to controlled alkaline modification. Under these conditions, deamidation and partial hydrolysis are expected to occur alongside broader structural and colloidal changes within the protein system. After modification, the dispersions were neutralized to a pH of 6-7, allowing for compatibility with ferric-salt sensitizers.

The resulting dispersions exhibited substantially altered physical behavior relative to native plant protein systems, including improved wetting, reduced viscosity, improved solution clarity, altered acidification behavior, and improved pigment dispersion and coating uniformity.

These observations are consistent with altered intermolecular interactions, aggregation behavior, and molecular weight distribution within the modified protein dispersions.

Fig. 3. 16% wheat protein dispersion after deamidation/hydrolysis, decant, settling and neutralization to pH 6.5.

3. Bench-Scale Observations

3.1 Ammonia Formation

Ammonia/ammonium formation was measured using colorimetric detection methods and increased over time during alkaline treatment. This observation is consistent with deamidation of glutamine and asparagine side chains under alkaline conditions.

Fig.4. Measured free ammonia in solution in a typical batch during alkaline treatment of wheat gluten dispersion. Free ammonia increased progressively over time, consistent with ongoing protein deamidation reactions.

3.2 Viscosity Reduction

Modified protein dispersions exhibited substantially reduced viscosity relative to native protein dispersions at equivalent solids concentration. This reduction is consistent with partial hydrolysis and reduced average molecular size, although deamidation and altered aggregation behavior may also contribute.

3.3 Surface Tension and Pigment Dispersion

Surface tension measurements indicated a substantial reduction during treatment. These changes correlated with improved substrate wetting, coating uniformity, and improved pigment wetting and dispersion behavior during coating preparation. This is consistent with the exposure of internal hydrophobic groups to the surface as treatment proceeds.

Increased levels of modification were also associated with reduced haze and improved solution clarity in aqueous dispersions, although the extent of these effects varied between different protein sources.

3.4 Dispersion Haze as an Indicator of Deamidation/Hydrolysis Degree

Wheat test samples that were processed longer have a higher degree of transparency. The cause is unknown, but it may be a protein-to-protein interaction or indicative of a change in the protein particle morphology or charge.

Fig. 5.
Progressive Processing Time
Left: W10: least processing time.
Right: W15: most processing time.

3.5 Low pH Induced Precipitation Behavior

Low level acidification of modified protein dispersions showed reduced precipitation and turbidity as deamidation and hydrolysis progressed. These shifts are consistent with altered charge density and a reduced isoelectric point arising from alkaline modification.

3.6 Storage Stability

Preserved modified protein dispersions remained stable at room temperature for periods of at least 18 months without noticeable phase separation or loss of coating functionality. While additional long-term characterization is required, these observations suggest useful storage stability for practical studio applications.

3.7 Drying Behavior and Coating Sensitivity

Coating performance was found to be sensitive to drying conditions during coating dry-down when incorporating ferric ammonium citrate (FAC) as sensitizer. In particular, wheat-based protein dispersions in comparison to soy or yellow pea, when sensitized with FAC produced substantially weaker and grittier final images when drying occurred slowly under ambient conditions. More rapid drying, including forced-air drying, produced stronger images with improved tonal range. This behavior was not observed in gelatin-based coatings prepared with FAC.

Microscopic examination of the wheat-based coatings subjected to slow dry-down suggested localized separation between protein-rich and FAC-rich zones within the coating layer during evaporation. One possible contributing factor involves concentration increases of FAC during evaporation, potentially influencing protein aggregation or partial salting-out behavior within the coating layer. Ion-specific dispersion instabilities described by the Hofmeister Series may contribute, as citrate is a known destabilizer at high concentrations, although additional investigation would be required to clarify the mechanism.

Preliminary observations suggest that the extent of this behavior may vary substantially between different plant protein sources. Among the protein systems examined, the effect appeared most pronounced in wheat-based protein dispersions. Comparable drying sensitivity in wheat was not observed with diazo- or DAS-based sensitizer systems under similar coating conditions.

4. Compatibility with Light-Sensitive Systems

The modified protein dispersions were found to be effectively crosslinked with multiple classes of light-sensitive systems such as ferric ammonium citrate/peroxide developer (FAC-P), DAS(Disodium 4,4'-diazidostilbene-2,2'-disulfonate tetrahydrate), and 4-Diazo (4-Diazodiphenylamine/formaldehyde condensate hydrogen sulfate, which are used in alternative photographic printing, photo stenciling and screen printing, indicating that the modified protein dispersions are not restricted to a single photochemical pathway. Slow-drying sensitivity in wheat was only observed with the FAC-P sensitizer system.

Among these systems, iron-based approaches represent the most accessible and comparatively lower-toxicity option within alternative photographic practice. Wide availability, established handling characteristics, and compatibility with existing studio workflows make them particularly relevant for sustainable implementation of modified protein-based imaging systems. DAS is also considered to be of low toxicity.

5. Imaging and Tonal Behavior

Emulsion coatings exposed to UV-rich light sources produced visible and repeatable image formation following aqueous dilute hydrogen peroxide development.

Observed characteristics included:

- differential solubility between exposed and unexposed regions
- retention of tonal structure after rinsing
- continuous tonal transitions under controlled exposure conditions
- sensitivity to coating thickness and treatment level

- Effective release of pigment from a paper substrate in unexposed areas

Inherent hydrophobic protein groups characteristic of gluten proteins may be responsible for the emulsions ability to sequester pigments, aiding washout in the image highlights. Practitioners are aware that casein, which is sometimes used in direct-carbon processes, is noted for its high pigment-clearing capacity. Casein also possesses a relatively large number of hydrophobic groups.

Lower levels of protein modification, produced by less aggressive high-pH treatment or shorter processing times, yielded higher-viscosity dispersions with faster apparent UV response. These conditions appeared particularly suited to direct photo screen-printing applications where rapid stencil formation, coating adhesion, and robustness are prioritized over continuous tonal behavior.

Moderate processing times improved dispersion, wetting, and tonal smoothness, but in excess; paper staining increased, emulsion speed slowed, and image density fell.

Fig. 6. Step wedge exposure tests of wheat dispersion + FAC on factory-sized paper, showing effective clearing of highlights despite high pigment loading.

Pigments left to right: phthalo blue, quinacridone magenta, nickel azo yellow, indanthrone, phthalo green.

6. Sustainability Considerations

The present work emphasizes not only reduced toxicity but also broader material sustainability.

Key aspects include:

- use of renewable plant-derived protein materials
- compatibility with comparatively lower-toxicity iron-based sensitizer systems
- reduced dependence on highly toxic dichromate processes
- reduced hazardous waste generation relative to heavy-metal chromium-based systems
- compatibility with accessible studio workflows and materials

While a full environmental assessment has not been conducted, these observations suggest a direction toward photographic materials emphasizing both reduced hazards and improved material sustainability.

7. Discussion

The combined observations suggest substantial alteration of protein behavior following high-pH treatment. Changes in wetting, viscosity, aggregation behavior, solubility, imaging sensitivity, and pigment dispersion appear to influence both liquid-state coating behavior and the properties of the final imaging layer. The resulting dried coatings functioned as active imaging matrices capable of supporting differential image formation following exposure and development.

In the FAC-P system, the well-known hardening mechanism likely involves iron-mediated peroxide reactions analogous to Fenton-type chemistry, influencing localized oxidation, crosslinking, or solubility changes within the modified protein layer.

Progressive deamidation/hydrolysis are expected to increase charge density while reducing average molecular size within the protein dispersions. These changes may increase intermolecular repulsion and reduce chain entanglement and cohesive behavior within the resulting films. Such effects may contribute to the observed changes in coating behavior, emulsion speed, film robustness, and photochemical insolubilization characteristics.

Although residual iron colouration was not visually obvious in the printed coatings, some residual iron species may remain within paper substrates or bound to protein within the image layer. Post-processing rinse baths containing citric acid or other environmentally safe chelating agents may therefore be useful for reducing residual iron content and improving long-term substrate and binder stability. Further work is required to better characterize the underlying mechanisms and long-term stability of the resulting prints.

8. Conclusion

This work demonstrates that controlled high-pH treatment of plant proteins can produce film-forming, photo-crosslinkable imaging systems compatible with contemporary alternative photographic workflows. Bench-scale observations support the occurrence of deamidation, partial hydrolysis, and broader structural modification, with resulting changes in wetting, viscosity, surface tension, pigment dispersion, haze reduction, exposure speed, and imaging behavior.

The compatibility of these modified protein systems with accessible iron-based sensitizer workflows suggests potential for further development of lower-toxicity and more materially sustainable photographic printing processes.

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